

The effect of end-tabbing methods on the tensile properties of electro-spun highly aligned PAN nano-fibres

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ABSTRACT

A novel electro-spinning method was used to produce highly aligned polyacrylonitrile (PAN) nano-fibre arrays. The tensile properties of the aligned fibres were investigated where three different adhesives were used in the end-tabs, namely, a photo-curable UV resin, super-glue and double-sided adhesive tape. The photo-curable UV adhesive and the super-glue were effective in enabling thorough impregnation of the nano-fibre arrays. However, the UV-resin offered greater control with regard to maintaining the impregnated area to within the end-tab region. On inspecting the stress/strain plots, it was concluded that the load-transfer from the end-tabs with the UV-adhesive was comparatively more uniform, repeatable and efficient. The ultimate tensile strength for the UV-adhesive, super-glue and double-sided adhesive tape were 76.71 ± 3.34 , 68.80 ± 4.41 and 67.38 ± 2.21 MPa respectively and the Young's moduli were 4.05 ± 1.17 , 2.50 ± 0.53 and 1.86 ± 0.53 GPa respectively. The failure strains for the test specimens with the three end-tab resins were similar and ranged between 22.46 ± 2.88 % and 23.73 ± 2.23 %. A phenomenological tensile model was applied to assess the tensile properties of the electro-spun PAN nano-fibres. The stress and stiffness calculated using the phenomenological tensile model were in agreement with the experimentally derived tensile data.

1. Introduction

Electro-spinning is a versatile technique for producing nano-fibres where a plethora of materials have been used, including polymers [1]; ceramics [2]; metals [3]; super-conductors [4], semi-conductors [5]; and biomaterials [6]. An attribute of nano-fibres is their relatively high specific area ($300\text{--}2800 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) [7], and this has led to applications relating to air filtration [8], catalysts [9] and water purification [10]. A schematic illustration of a typical needle-based electro-spinning experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1.

The electro-spinning process generally begins with the filling of the syringe with a filtered polymer solution and attaching it to a liquid dispensing unit. A hypodermic needle is attached to the syringe and connected to a high-voltage power supply whose polarity can be selected as desired. The dispensing unit is set to deliver and maintain a pendant drop of the polymer solution at the tip of the needle once the necessary temperature and humidity levels have been achieved. The high-voltage power supply is switched on and the applied voltage is increased gradually, and this leads to the solution becoming charged. Coulombic

repulsion [11] between the components of the solution increase as the applied voltage is increased. These charges accumulate on the surface of the pendant drop, and concurrently, there is attraction between the charges on the pendant drop and the grounded electrode. As the applied voltage is increased further, the pendant polymer drop deforms into a conical shape; this is referred to as the Taylor cone [12]. At a critical applied voltage, there comes a point when repulsive surface charges within the Taylor cone overcome the surface tension of the polymer solution and a fine polymer 'jet' is ejected from the tip of the cone. The charged polymer jet accelerates towards the grounded electrode where it follows a relatively straight path for a certain length from the tip of the Taylor cone. After this short straight trajectory, the jet undergoes considerable whipping where its diameter decreases significantly; this aids the evaporation of the solvent and the formation of a skin on the fibres. The whipping of the polymer is generally uncontrolled, resulting in it being deposited in a random orientation on the grounded electrode. Several studies have reported on techniques to counteract the whipping motion or to control it, thereby enabling the production of aligned nano-fibres. Such techniques include the use of: a rotating mandrel [13];

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Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of a conventional electro-spinning rig. The key components are: (i) precision liquid dispensing unit; (ii) syringe for housing the polymer solution; (iii) hypodermic needle; (iv) grounded electrode; (v) high-voltage power supply; (vi) heater; (vii) silica gel; and (viii) electro-spinning chamber (doors not shown).

centrifugal alignment [14]; parallel electrodes where the electric [15] and magnetic [16] fields are controlled; insulating blocks [17]; and auxiliary electrodes [18].

In some applications, it is preferable to produce nano-fibres that are aligned. In the event that the aligned nano-fibres are to be used in the production of preforms for high-performance composites, they need to be continuous; such a production process was reported by the authors previously [19].

Regardless of the end-use application area for electro-spun nano-fibres, assessing their mechanical properties is an important prerequisite. Several distinctive experimental set-ups have been designed and used to characterise the tensile properties of various types of electro-spun polymer nano-fibres. A summary of selected test methods for electro-spun nano-fibre is presented in the supplementary materials section (Table SM1). Examples of equipment that have been used to characterise the tensile properties of the nano-fibres include conventional tensile test machines [20], micro/nano tensile testers [21], atomic force microscopy-based systems [22], micro-electromechanical systems [23] and dynamic mechanical analysis-based instrumentation [24]. However, unlike the mechanical testing of nonwoven fabrics (ISO 9073; BS EN 29073), macro-fibres (ASTM D3822, ISO 11566), bulk polymers (ASTM D638, ISO 527) and composites (ASTM D2343, ISO 524, ISO 1172), where relevant ASTM, BS, EN and ISO standards exist, the same is not true for evaluating nano-fibres [25]. Therefore, it is difficult to compare datasets from different publications (see Table SM1) because the test parameters (load-cell capacity, method of load application, cross-head displacement rate, temperature and humidity) and specimen preparation methods (gauge length, width, thickness, cross-sectional area, fibre volume fraction and end-tapping method) differ significantly. Measuring the fibre volume fraction, cross-sectional area and thickness of the nano-fibrous mat accurately is challenging because of the relatively high intrinsic porosity and the low packing density that is associated with electro-spun mats [26,27]. However, determining the previously mentioned properties is essential in order to characterise the mechanical properties of electro-spun fibre bundles and mats.

With reference to Table SM1, in the case of scaffolds, the volume fraction was calculated by dividing the calculated scaffold density by the known density of the parent polymer [28]. The calculated density of the

scaffold was obtained by dividing the mass of the scaffold with the volume of the scaffold. It is assumed that the fibres are free of voids and solvent, and that the crystallinity and the density of the as-received polymer is the same as the electro-spun fibres. The thickness of the electro-spun samples is generally obtained from micrographs of their cross-sections [29] or using a digital micrometer [26,28,30–32]. The cross-sectional area obtained from the above-mentioned methods largely depends on the measurement condition (e.g. applied pressure) and resolution of the selected measuring equipment [25]. In order to avoid compressing the sample during the thickness measurements, white light profilometry [33], transmitted light intensity through the nano-fibre preform [34] and laser interferometry [35] have been used.

Maccaferri et al. [25], calculated the tensile properties of electro-spun preforms using a grammage normalisation approach. They reported a linear relationship between the grammage and cross-sectional area where the slope varied according to the morphology of the nano-fibres. In their study, the stress was derived by normalising the applied force over the grammage rather than the thickness of the sample. Their findings indicated that grammage normalisation procedure was less precise than mass-based normalisation but more effective than the cross-sectional area-based approach [25].

In contrast to assessments of randomly oriented nanofiber membranes, evaluations of aligned electro-spun nano-fibre arrays or bundles can provide a better representation of the intrinsic tensile properties of the nano-fibres themselves. In the case of tensile testing conventional synthetic fibres such as E-glass and carbon fibres, single-fibre tensile tests (ASTM D3822, ASTM C1557-20, ISO 11566), and fibre bundle/tow tests (ASTM D4018, ASTM D2343-17) are used. Fibre bundles are generally easier to extract, handle and perform tensile tests when compared to single-fibres. However, in the case of tensile testing bundles, the interactions between fibres can have an effect on the measured properties [36]. Nevertheless, they are still comparatively simpler than the evaluation of a single nano-fibre.

With regard to tensile testing of nano-fibres, an effective end-tab design is required to protect the specimen from being damaged by the serrated grip surfaces [37]. Furthermore, the selection of the adhesive is important to enable effective load transfer from the grips to the fibres [38].

With reference to Table SM1, typical materials used as the adhesive for the end-tabs for evaluating nano-fibre mats include epoxy adhesives [39], double-sided adhesive tape [40] and adhesive cushion tape [20]. However, not all publications provide details about the end-tabs or the nature of the adhesive that was used to bond the section of the fibres that are within the end-tabs. When tensile testing fibre bundles, due care and attention needs to be taken to ensure that the adhesive does not wick into the fibres within the gauge length [41].

The primary aims of the current paper were: (i) to select an adhesive for the end-tabs; and (ii) to develop an end-tapping method to assess the tensile properties of unidirectional electro-spun PAN nano-fibres that were produced using the Vee-shield [19] nano-fibre alignment method.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) was purchased from Goodfellow, UK, in powder form, with an average molecular weight of 230,000 g/mol. DMSO with a purity of 99.9 %, was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, UK. The PAN solutions were prepared in a 250 ml 3-neck round bottom flask under reflux. In addition to using a magnetic stirrer to agitate the polymer solution, dry nitrogen gas was bubbled into the liquid at 10 ml/min. The refluxing was carried out for 6 h at 60 °C. The polymer concentration was 12 wt/vol% in DMSO. Double-sided adhesive tape (Ryman, UK), super-glue (Loctite 403, UK) and UV-cure resin (Norland optical adhesive 68, USA) were used as the end-tab adhesives.

2.2. Electro-spinning equipment

The electro-spinning equipment used in this study is identical to that used by Shao et al. [19]. The refluxed PAN/DMSO solution was drawn into a 5 ml syringe (Terumo, UK) and secured in a liquid dispenser unit (NE-300, World Precision Instruments, UK). A PTFE tube (Masterflex transfer tubing, Cole-Parmer, UK) was used to attach a 20 mm length flat tip 25-gauge needle with inner and outer bore diameters of 0.3 and 0.5 mm respectively (Adhesive Dispensing Ltd, UK) to the syringe. A polypropylene female Lure lock adapter to a 1/8" barb fitting (Cole-Parmer Item # UY-45508-34, UK) was used as the connector between the syringe and tubing, and a polypropylene male lure adapter to 1/8" ID hose barb fitting (Cole-Parmer Item # WZ-45518-26, UK) was used as the connector between the needle and tubing. The needle was attached to the positive output of a high-voltage DC power supply (73030, Genvolt, UK) via a copper ring (0.5 mm ID, 0.8 mm OD, 1 mm thickness). The applied voltage was maintained at 14 kV throughout the electro-spinning process. The chamber temperature and relative humidity were maintained at 55 ± 4 °C and 13 ± 4 %, respectively. Chamber temperature was regulated using a 175 W infrared lamp (IR 175R E27 Infrared Bulb, Phillips, UK) and a 40 cm portable storage heater (Dimplex, UK). The portable storage heater was only used to preheat the chamber and was removed prior to electro-spinning. The temperature and RH were monitored using a digital thermometer-hygrometer (RS Pro, RS Components, UK).

2.3. Vee-shield collector

The custom-designed grounded collector, referred to as the Vee-shield collector, was used to produce aligned PAN nano-fibres. This set-up was previously described by the authors [19] and only a brief description is presented here. A schematic illustration of the set-up of the Vee-shield method is shown in Fig. 2(a). The coded items (i-viii) in Fig. 2(a) are identical to those cited in Fig. 1. The new items in Fig. 2(a) are: (ix) represents an additional heat source; and (x) is the Vee-shield rig. An expanded view of the Vee-shield rig is shown in Fig. 2(b). It was constructed from a sheet of PTFE (Direct Plastic, UK) with dimensions of 10 cm width, 25 cm length and 3 mm thickness (item xi); the angles of the Vee-shield were set at 65° in relation to the vertical plane. The flat section of the Vee-shield (item xii) was 6 mm wide and 100 mm long. A black craft paper (80 gsm, Ryman, UK) strip with dimensions of 0.6 cm \times 100 mm \times 0.1 mm was used as the static substrate for collecting aligned nano-fibres. The grounded electrode is represented by item

(xiii). The distance between the tip of the needle and the centre point of the paper substrate was set at 100 mm. The fibre alignment direction is shown by the arrow in Fig. 2(b). With reference to Fig. 2, the introduction of the V-shaped PTFE fixture (Vee-shield) alters the electric field configuration. The PTFE Vee-shield effectively confines the electric potential between the needle and the collector. COMSOL modeling (Figure SM2) revealed that the Vee-shield reduces the charge density and electric field strength at the edges of the electrodes along the YX-plane. This creates a focused 'channel' of electric field strength along the YZ-plane, effectively redirecting the charged polymer jet. The resulting potential difference guides the charged polymer jet along a preferential path within the Vee-shield setup. This redirection induces controlled oscillations of the polymer jet between the ends of the grounded electrode, producing highly aligned nano-fibres. The solution feed rate was maintained at 0.01 ml/h, and the electro-spinning was carried out for 1 h for each sample.

2.4. Recovery of the aligned nano-fibres

The aligned nano-fibres were prepared using the Vee-shield method as described above. Prior to removing the nano-fibres and paper substrate from the collector, an 18 mm diameter rotary cutter was used to cut along the edge of the 6 mm \times 65 mm paper substrate. Removing the substrate without this step was observed to disrupt the alignment of the nano-fibres within the gauge length due to the interference from the fibres that were deposited outside the desired width.

The as-spun aligned nano-fibre arrays with dimensions 65 mm \times 6 mm were separated from the substrate and transferred to a paper frame (see Fig. 3) with dimensions as shown in Fig. 3(a). In order to enable alignment of the nano-fibre array and easy sectioning, a 20 mm gridded paper (100 gsm, VIZAL, UK) was used. The outer frame was sectioned with a steel craft knife (Olfa, UK). The inner frame was cut using a hand-held cutter punch (CUT50-18, My-Accessories, UK) that enabled reproducible dimensions of the frame to be produced. Two 24 mm \times 8 mm double-sided adhesive tape sections (GTSE, China) were placed on the top and bottom of the paper frame (see Fig. 3(b)). Fig. 3(c) shows the paper frame and the top surface of the electro-spun fibres. The as-spun nano-fibre sample was attached to the frame with the fibre-side down and the craft paper on the surface, as shown in Fig. 3(d). Following this, the craft paper substrate was peeled off carefully from the nano-fibre array (see Fig. 3(e)). A 20 mm wide sellotape (Ryman, UK) was placed at the top and bottom of the frame and gentle manual tension was applied to the fibre array as it was adhered to the sellotape (see Fig. 3(f)).

Fig. 2. Schematic illustrations of: (a) the custom-designed Vee-shield grounded electrode configuration for producing aligned nano-fibres; and (b) an enlarged schematic illustration of the Vee-shield collector. See text for details.

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic diagram showing the dimensions of the nano-fibre strip/bundle (grey) and the paper frame (green); the dimensions are in mm, and (b–g) photographs of the sample transfer procedure of the as-spun random and aligned nano-fibres (see text for details). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

After that, another paper frame of the same dimensions but with double-sided adhesive tape placed on top of the original frame was used to form a sandwich structure (see Fig. 3(g)). Finally, the excess sellotape outside the frame was cut, and the sample with frame assembly was stored in a desiccator until required. The paper frame was observed to maintain the tension in the aligned fibre array during storage and it also prevented it from curling during subsequent operations.

2.5. Drying regime for the electro-spun nano-fibres

It was necessary to remove any residual solvent in the electro-spun fibres prior to tensile testing. Low manual tension was applied to the fibre array in the paper frame, and it was fixed onto the Teflon-coated metal tray using heat-resistant tape (3M, 8992, UK). The samples were heated from the ambient temperature at 10 K/min to 120 °C under 1 mbar with a dwell time of 6 h, after which the vacuum oven was turned off and permitted to cool naturally to ambient temperature. The fibre samples with the paper frame were removed and stored in a desiccator

Fig. 4. (a–d) Photographs showing the sequential steps that were taken to manufacture the tensile test specimens.

until required.

2.6. Preparation of tensile test specimens

With reference to Fig. 4(a), the dried nano-fibre sample with the frame was removed from the desiccator and placed on 2 mm grid graph paper. The free-ends of the paper frame were secured to the graph paper using masking tape. A polyethylene terephthalate (PET) window frame (dimensions of 30 mm (length) * 20 mm (width) for the outer window frame and 15 mm * 15 mm for the inner window frame), was positioned carefully underneath the nano-fibre array such that the fibres were parallel to the left and right sides of the inner vertical edges of the PET frame (Fig. 4(a)). The edges of the paper frame were lifted gently with a pair of plastic-tipped tweezers to ensure that the fibres did not rub against the plastic frame at any stage during sample preparation. After verifying the relative positions of the various items, approximately 28 μ l of UV resin (Norland optical adhesive 68, USA) was dispensed evenly across the width and length of the intended end-tab bonding area at the top and bottom of the test frame using a micro-pipette (m100, Biohit, UK), (see Fig. 4(b)). Due care and attention were paid to ensure that the impregnation was thorough and without any visual signs of under-impregnation or the presence of air bubbles. Special attention was also given to ensure that the adhesive did not wick into the gauge length of the test specimen. After the end-tab region was impregnated, another identical PET frame was placed on the top, precisely over the frame below, with the fibres sandwiched in between. Two thickness-gauges (spacers) of 0.6 mm were placed on either side of the paper frame, and a glass sheet (dimensions of 26 mm width, 76 mm length and 2 mm thickness with a weight of 2.4 g) was placed on top of the whole assembly, and two 100 g weights were placed on the top of the spacers; this assembly is shown in Fig. 4(c). This assembly was used to maintain the bond line thickness across all the samples. The whole assembly was permitted to stand for 1 min before a UV light source with an intensity of 40 mW and wavelength between 300 and 425 nm (Thorlabs 560 UV-75, UK) was used to cross-link the adhesive. Due to the thickness of the UV resin, the UV irradiation was carried out in three cycles, with 30 s per cycle. After the adhesive had cross-linked, the fibres that were protruding outside the PET frame were cut using the rotary blade (Fig. 4(d)). The samples were labelled and stored in a desiccator until required for testing. The procedure was repeated as appropriate when superglue and double-sided adhesive tape were used as end-tab adhesives.

2.7. Tensile testing

The tensile properties of the nano-fibre arrays were evaluated using an Instron (US) 5566 universal testing machine with a 10 N load-cell. The grips used were a fibre filament micro tensile grip (2711-006 series, Instron, UK). The gripped area was 36 mm² and it had an adjustable clamping force and self-aligning hard rubber-coated faces which had a maximum load capacity of 5 N. The tests were carried out in a temperature-regulated laboratory at 24 \pm 2 °C and RH at 20 \pm 4 %. The rectangular and framed test specimens were used for the tensile tests. Before tensile testing, the gauge length and width of each sample was measured from photographs using Image-J. Each sample was measured five times and the data were averaged. A digital micrometer was used to measure the thickness of each test specimen. When securing the sample in the jaws of the test machine, attention was paid to ensure that the fibres were parallel to the principal loading direction. Before starting the tensile loading, the sides of the plastic frame were cut to ensure that only the fibres were held in the grips (as shown in Fig. 5). The load and the displacement were zeroed, and the crosshead displacement rate was set to 1 mm per minute with the load/displacement data being recorded. A set of three repeat experiments were done for each end-tapping method. Bluehill 3 software was used to record the load/displacement data.

Fig. 5. Photograph of a tensile test sample mounted on the gripping fixture of the tensile tester.

2.8. Scanning electron microscopy

The surface morphology of aligned fibres, as well as the degree of impregnation within the end-tab region were inspected using a Hitachi TM3030plus tabletop scanning electron microscope (SEM). The instrument was operated at 15 kV. The electro-spun fibre mats were mounted onto a circular SEM aluminium stub using double-sided conductive carbon adhesive tape. The fibres were sputter-coated with gold/palladium alloy for 3 min using an Emscope SC 500 vacuum sputter-coater to render the sample conductive.

2.9. Transmission electron microscopy

A JEOL JEM-1400 transmission electron microscope (TEM) was used to inspect the cross-section of the electro-spun fibres and hence to measure fiber diameter. The aligned nano-fibre samples in the tensile test frame were placed in a PTFE mould with dimensions of 25 mm \times 32 mm \times 20 mm. The fibres were impregnated using a mixture of 3 ml Araldite CY212 resin, 5 ml AGAR 100 (Epon substitute), 13 ml DDSA (hardener), 0.6 ml DBP (plasticiser) and 0.5 ml DMP 30 (Accelerator) to obtain a total of 22 ml of the liquid resin. The assembly was placed in a vacuum oven (Gallenkamp, UK) for 6 h to degas the resin and to impregnate the fibres. Finally, the mould with the impregnated fibres and resin were cross-linked in an oven at 60 °C for 24 h. The sample was microtomed (ULTRACUT, UK) into 100 nm thick and 30 μ m wide sections using a diamond-tipped blade (Ultra 1436, DIATOME, Switzerland) using a sectioning speed of 1 mm/s. Each section was deposited onto a 200 mesh copper TEM grid (Agar Scientific, UK). 10 micrographs were captured per sample, and thirty micrographs were recorded. Image-J software was used to measure the cross-sectional area of the fibres.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Assessment of the end-tab adhesives

Fig. 6(a–c) show optical micrographs of the end-tabs where the UV

Fig. 6. Photographs of the end-tab region using different end-tab adhesives. The type of adhesive that used in the end-tabs were: (a) UV-curable adhesive; (b) Super-glue; and (c) Double-sided adhesive tape.

Fig. 7. (a–i) Micrograph of end-tabbed samples that were sectioned in liquid nitrogen: (a) the cross-section of the tensile test frame and the end-tab region for the UV adhesive. The arrow indicates where the composite delaminated from the end-tab after it was immersed in liquid nitrogen and fractured; (b) magnified micrograph showing some of the nano-fibres; (c) illustration of the case where the end-tab resin (UV curable adhesive) did not wick into the gauge length; (d) an example where the super-glue end-tab adhesive had penetrated the gauge length; (e) typical appearance of a sample where double-sided adhesive tape was used as the adhesive – the unravelling of the nano-fibres is a consequence of them not being fully secured or bonded; (f) appearance of the tensile test specimen showing minimal meandering of the nano-fibres after the edges were trimmed using a rotary cutter; (g) micrograph showing the extent of fibre alignment in the electro-spun sample; (h) the degree of fibre orientation for the electro-spun aligned PAN nano-fibres; and (i) TEM micrograph showing individual and separated fibres (red) and fibres with minimal fusion (blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

resin, super-glue and double-sided tape were used as the adhesive. The purpose of the end-tapped region is to distribute the gripping force evenly through the frame and for the applied load to be transferred to the fibres efficiently and uniformly. After the test specimens were produced, the thickness of the frame and fibre sandwich structure was measured using a digital micrometer. As seen in Fig. 6(a–c), the average thickness of the end-tapped regions when the double-sided adhesive tape, super-glue and the UV resin were used was 0.712 ± 0.05 mm, 0.650 ± 0.01 mm and 0.652 ± 0.01 mm, respectively. The measurement resolution of a digital micrometer was 10 μ m or about 1.5 % of the specimen thickness [41].

In the current study, the nature of the adhesive on the double-sided adhesive tape meant that it was not efficient in impregnating the fibres in the through-thickness direction. In other words, only the fibres on the surfaces were anchored by the adhesive. The loading of the nano-fibres in the sub surfaces were most likely via fibre entanglements. The end-tabs fabricated from super-glue showed an uneven bond-line thickness. Since the super-glue adhesive that was used had a fast-curing time and relatively low-viscosity, it was not possible to obtain a uniform bonded area from sample-to-sample. Furthermore, the super-glue wicked readily into the gauge length region. This meant the processing window for sample preparation and control was rather limited. A conventional two-part epoxy/amine resin was also evaluated. Although, the curing time was around 20 h at room temperature, preventing the resin from wicking into the gauge length region could not be controlled in a repeatable manner. Applying heat to accelerate the curing was attempted, but it resulted in unacceptable shrinkage. In the case of the UV-curable adhesive, the rapid increase in the viscosity upon UV irradiation meant that the degree of impregnation, as observed visually, and the control of the impregnated area was significantly superior when compared to the other methods discussed above. Furthermore, the observed shrinkage was also negligible.

SEM micrographs of the end-tab regions for the adhesives are shown in Fig. 7(a–e). These samples were obtained by sectioning the end-tapped region in liquid nitrogen. In Fig. 7(a), a relatively uniform composite (PAN nano-fibres in UV resin) thickness is seen for the UV resin-bonded end-tab where the average thickness was 57 ± 6 μ m. The arrow indicates the delamination between the end-tab and the composite. The delamination was caused when the end-tab assembly was immersed in liquid nitrogen and sectioned with a pair of scissors. Fig. 7(b) shows a magnified micrograph of the PAN nano-fibres in the UV resin. On inspecting Fig. 7(b), it is evident that each nano-fibre in the arrays are impregnated fully by the UV resin. The observed fibre pull-out is possibly due to drawing and shearing of the nano-fibres and shrinkage when the sample was immersed in liquid nitrogen and sectioned. In order to maintain the desired gauge length of the test specimen for subsequent tensile testing, it was important for the end-tab resin not to wick into the gauge length region. This was achieved when the photocurable UV resins was used as the end-tab adhesive where it is clear from Fig. 7(c) that gauge length region was not impregnated. An example where the end-tab adhesive wicked into the gauge length and impregnated the PAN nano-fibres is presented in Fig. 7(d), where super-glue was used. Fig. 7(e) represents the aftermath of fracturing the sample in liquid nitrogen where double-sided adhesive tape was used to “bond” the aligned nano-fibre arrays to the end-tab. Since only the surface layers of the nano-fibres are secured by the double-sided adhesive tape, upon immersion and sectioning in liquid nitrogen, delamination occurred as stated previously. However, in this case, the sectioned fibres were free to unravel and lose their original orientation (see Fig. 7(e)). The perturbations to the aligned nano-fibres at the edge where they were sectioned using the rotary cutter is shown in Fig. 7(f). The degree of fibre alignment achieved using the Vee-shield method is illustrated in Fig. 7(g) and the corresponding distribution of the orientation angle of the nano-fibres is shown in Fig. 7(h) where the narrow distribution of fibre angles is apparent. The TEM micrograph presented in Fig. 7(i) shows that the majority of nano-fibres were unfused and that

the as-spun fibres have a near-circular cross-section. 30 individual TEM micrographs were inspected, and about $63 \pm 4\%$ of the fibres in those frames showed a minimal degree of fusion at the contact points. The observed fusion is probably due to the slow solidification of the skin on the fibres during cooling. The fibre diameter distribution as measured using image analysis of the TEM micrographs was 326.9 ± 45.4 nm.

3.2. Effect of the end-tapping adhesive on the tensile test results

As described in the introduction, the tensile test results can be influenced significantly by the end-tapping method, adhesive type and quality [37,42]. Fig. 8 illustrates typical stress–strain traces for the electro-spun aligned PAN nano-fibres with the different end-tab bonding adhesives. Here, the thickness of the specimen was obtained using a digital micrometer. The width was determined using optical micrographs and Image-J software. A summary of the measurements, as well as the end-tapping adhesive used and the average tensile test results are presented in Table 1. Additional representative stress/strain plots for the three types of end-tab adhesives are presented in SM3.

With reference to Fig. 8, and the data presented in Table 1, the average ultimate tensile strength (UTS) for the end-tab bonding methods using the UV adhesive, super-glue and double-sided adhesive tape were 76.71 ± 3.34 , 68.80 ± 4.41 and 67.38 ± 2.21 MPa respectively; the corresponding average Young’s modulus were 4.05 ± 1.17 , 2.50 ± 0.53 and 1.86 ± 0.53 GPa respectively. The average failure strain for the UV adhesive, super-glue and double-sided adhesive tape were 23.26 ± 1.46 , 23.73 ± 2.23 , 22.46 ± 2.88 % respectively.

In Table 1, dimensions of the widths were obtained from optical micrographs and image analysis. The measurements were taken after the samples were end-tapped and therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the lateral movement of the fibres in the gauge length would be minimal. Measuring the thickness of the sample using the digital micrometer on the other hand depends on the magnitude to which the sample can be compressed. Given the intrinsic porosity of the electro-spun fibres, a degree of compaction during the measurement is to be expected. Here, the porosity was calculated based on the volume of the tensile specimen and, the volume of the nano-fibres was calculated using the weight of the nano-fibre array and the density of the electro-spun fibres. The failure load can be influenced by several factors including the following. The number of nano-fibres in the sample, the flaw density in the fibres, the gauge length, degree of alignment of the nano-fibres in relation to the loading axis and the efficiency of the loading of the fibres within the end-

Fig. 8. Typical stress–strain traces for the electro-spun aligned PAN nano-fibres where the end-tabs adhesive were a photo-curable UV resin, super-glue and double-sided adhesive tape.

Table 1

Summary of the end-tapping method, dimensions and tensile test results for the electro-spun aligned PAN nano-fibre bundles. The gauge length was 15 mm and the cross-head displacement rate was 0.1 mm/min.

No.	Property	UV Adhesive	Super-glue Adhesive	Double-sided Adhesive Tape	Statistical Analysis Using F-Test	
					P - Value	Confidence level of 95 %
Physical Properties						
1	Diameter of Nano-fibres, nm	326.9 ± 45.4				–
2	Porosity, %	54.6 ± 0.5	58.8 ± 4.7	59.3 ± 2.8	0.250	Not statistically significant.
3	Thickness, μm	3.90 ± 0.20	4.10 ± 0.17	4.10 ± 0.10	0.296	Not statistically significant.
4	Mat density, g/cm ³	0.527 ± 0.005	0.478 ± 0.044	0.472 ± 0.032	0.250	Not statistically significant.
5	Total equivalent length, m	5.30 E6 ± 2.26 E5	4.57 E6 ± 1.44 E5	4.62 E6 ± 1.46 E5	0.127	Not statistically significant.
6	Expected number of crossings	5.89 E12 ± 6.19 E11	6.66 E12 ± 4.29 E11	6.81 E12 ± 4.33 E11	0.130	Not statistically significant.
Tensile Properties						
7	Ultimate tensile strength (UTS), MPa	76.71 ± 3.34	68.80 ± 4.41	67.38 ± 2.21	0.032	Statistically significant.
8	Young Modulus, GPa	4.05 ± 1.17	2.50 ± 0.53	1.86 ± 0.53	0.039	Statistically significant.
9	Strain at max. stress, %	10.43 ± 0.94	12.86 ± 2.60	15.71 ± 2.59	0.067	Not statistically significant.
10	Strain at failure, %	23.26 ± 1.46	23.73 ± 2.23	22.46 ± 2.88	0.793	Not statistically significant.

tabs. The samples represented in Table 1 were produced after electro-spinning each sample for 60 min and the electro-spinning conditions were as similar as practically possible. Therefore, the nominal thicknesses for each sample per batch should be similar.

Statistical analyses (F-test) were performed on the UTS, Young's modulus, strain at maximum stress and the strain at failure. Using a confidence level of 95%, the null hypothesis for the UTS and the Young's modulus were rejected; this means that UTS and Young's modulus of the PAN nano-fibres were influenced significantly by end-tab adhesive. The PAN nano-fibres with UV adhesive end-tabs offered the highest UTS and Young's modulus when compared to the end-tab test specimens that were produced using superglue and double-sided tape. The possible reasons for the superior performance of the UV end-tab adhesive are as follows: (i) the viscosity of the uncured resin meant that it could ensure thorough impregnation of nano-fibres; (ii) the benefit of the photocurable resin is that it was possible to control the impregnation front whereby it is prevented from entering the gauge length region; and (iii) since the impregnation was thorough and the resin cross-linked fully, it is proposed that the load-transfer from the matrix to nano-fibres was efficient. In the case of the double-sided tape-based end-tab adhesive, it meant that only the outer layers of the fibres were loaded in the first instance, and the subsequent loading of the filaments is possibly due to inter-fibre entanglement as the sample is loaded in tension. Therefore, the load-transfer is likely not to be as efficient when compared to the case where the region within the end-tabs is a solid, as is the case with the cross-linked UV adhesive. The performance of the super-glue may have been due to its low viscosity where it was difficult to control the impregnated area. The F-tests analyses were also applied to the strain at maximum stress and the failure strain datasets. In this case, the null hypotheses were accepted and therefore it was concluded that these parameters were not influenced significantly by end-tab adhesive.

3.3. Phenomenological tensile model

The total or equivalent length (l_{eq}) and the number of crossings in the nano-fibrous mat were calculated using the formula given by Maccaferri [25]:

$$l_{eq} = \frac{4m}{\rho_m \pi} \frac{1}{d^2} \quad (1)$$

$$n_c^{fibers} = \frac{16m^2}{\rho_m^2 \pi^3} \frac{1}{d^2} \quad (2)$$

where, ρ_m , m and d are the mat density, mass and density of the nano-fibres respectively. The equivalent length for the three different end-tab adhesives is not significantly different. The equivalent length (l_{eq}) is based on an area of m^2 whereas the number of crossings is 1 g of nano-fibres within an area of $1 m^2$. In Equation (2), n_c^{fibers} is the number of

crossings per unit area. The total length and the number of crossings is not significantly different for three different end-tab adhesives. It is concluded that the physical properties of aligned PAN nano-fibres are similar for three different end-tab adhesives.

The phenomenological tensile model developed by Maccaferri [25] was used here to describe the stress-strain curves of the electro-spun aligned PAN mats. The calculated stress was expressed as the superimposition of a linear stress (σ_1) and a nonlinear (σ_2) stress [25]:

$$\sigma(\epsilon) = \sigma_1(\epsilon) - \sigma_2(\epsilon) \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma(\epsilon) = (a\epsilon + b) - (b\epsilon^{-c}) \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma(\epsilon) = a\epsilon + b(1 - e^{-c\epsilon}) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\epsilon} = E(\epsilon) = a + bce^{-c\epsilon} \quad (6)$$

where, $\sigma(\epsilon)$ and $E(\epsilon)$ are the stress and stiffness as a function of strain ϵ . a , b and c are constants and they are determined by applying appropriate values to the stress and strain data. Fig. 9(a) shows the calculated stress and stiffness using Equations (5) and (6), respectively. The stress calculated using the phenomenological model shows a good correlation with the experimental results up to the maximum stress or ultimate tensile stress (UTS). Similar constants (a , b and c) were used in Equation (6) to calculate the stiffness $E(\epsilon)$ as function of strain as shown on Fig. 9 (b); once again, a good correlation is observed between the experimental and calculated values.

Fig. 10 shows the constants a , b and c that were used for the modeling iterations for the three end-tab adhesives. The constant “ a ” was not significantly different for the three different end-tab adhesives. With reference to Equations (3)–(7), the constant “ a ” is only related to the linear stress σ_1 . However, constants “ b ” and “ c ” are significantly different for the three different end-tab adhesives. Constant “ b ” gives a contribution to both the linear stress σ_1 and non-linear stress σ_2 . Maccaferri et al. [25], reported that the constant “ b ” is related to the morphology of the nano-fibrous mat and in particular that it is related to the number of intersections. In the current study, the reason for the different constant “ b ” may be attributed to the significant variation in the efficiency of load-transfer from adhesive to the nano-fibres during tensile loading. As discussed previously, the UV end-tab adhesive displayed higher stiffness values when compared to the other two classes of adhesive. At low strain values or in the elastic region, Equation (6) can be represented as:

$$E_0 = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} E(\epsilon) = a + bc \quad (7)$$

The Young's modulus or E_0 can be predicted by knowing the constants “ a ”, “ b ” and “ c ”.

Constant “ c ” in the phenomenological model is related to the non-

Fig. 9. (a) Tensile stress and (b) stiffness calculated using the phenomenological model for the UV end-tab adhesive.

Fig. 10. Values for the constant (a, b and c) used in the phenomenological model.

linear stress σ_2 and it also contributes to the calculation of Young's modulus as described in Equation (7). Constants "b" and "c" for the UV adhesive end-tabs, and the Young's modulus are higher than those for super-glue and double-sided adhesive tape end-tabs. The value of $(1/c)$ also represents the onset extrapolation of the slope change from a linear region to a non-linear one or known as "knee strain" ϵ_{knee} . The knee strains for the UV, super-glue and double-side adhesive tape are 0.013 %, 0.019 % and 0.025 %, respectively.

Wan and Ko [43] investigated the relationship between the tensile properties of an individual nano-fibre and that of nano-fibre assemblies through geometric analysis. They found that the tensile strength of a randomly oriented nano-fibre mat is a function of fibre packing density (porosity), test specimen dimension (width-to-length ratio), and the tensile strength of a single nano-fibre. They developed a model to calculate the tensile strength of aligned nano-fibres:

$$\sigma = \frac{(1-P)[(1+k^2) \cdot \text{artg}(k) + k]^2}{2\pi k(1+k^2)^{3/2}} \sigma_f \quad (8)$$

where, σ and σ_f are the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of the nano-fibre assemblies and single nano-fibre respectively. The packing density or

porosity of nano-fibre assemblies is labelled as P , and K is the ratio of width-to-length of the tensile specimen. Equation (8) is rearranged to calculate the UTS of the nano-fibres based on the tensile strength data of the randomly aligned nano-fibres.

$$\sigma_f = \frac{2\pi k(1+k^2)^{3/2}}{(1-P)[(1+k^2) \cdot \text{artg}(k) + k]^2} \sigma \quad (9)$$

The tensile strength of single PAN nano-fibre is calculated from the tensile strength or UTS of aligned PAN nano-fibres and the packing density (porosity) listed in Table 1. The tensile strength of single PAN nano-fibre with the UV adhesives is calculated to be 696.70 ± 30.55 MPa. Where the tensile strengths of single PAN nano fiber with the super-glue and double-side adhesive tape are 681.31 ± 15.78 MPa and 669.01 ± 16.64 MPa respectively.

Wan and Ko [43] also developed a model to correlate the tensile modulus of aligned PAN nano-fibres to that of a single nano-fibres:

$$E_f = \frac{6\pi\theta \cdot \sin \theta}{(1-P)(\theta + 2 \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta)(\theta + \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta)^2} E \quad (10)$$

where, E and E_f are the tensile modulus of the nano-fibre assemblies and single nano-fibre respectively. " θ " is the diagonal angle to the longitudinal axis of the sample being tested.

The tensile modulus of single PAN nano-fibre was calculated from the tensile modulus of the aligned PAN nano-fibre arrays using Equation (9). The tensile strength of a single PAN nano-fibre with the UV adhesive end-tab is calculated to be 41.45 ± 12.08 GPa. Whereas the tensile moduli for a single PAN nano-fibre with the super-glue and double-sided adhesive tape are 27.90 ± 4.54 GPa and 21.08 ± 6.89 GPa respectively.

With reference to Table SMI1, it is readily apparent that the tensile strength and Young's modulus for PAN-based electro-spun fibres vary significantly. As mentioned previously, comparing data for the mechanical properties of electro-spun fibre is difficult because the fibre production methods, solvent used, molecular weight distribution, polymer concentration, end-tapping method, gauge length, measurement of the cross-sectional area and the test methods differ significantly. The following conclusions can be drawn from the mechanical test data presented in Table SMI1 for electro-spun PAN fibres: (i) The tensile strengths and Young's moduli vary between 45 and 178 MPa [references 3, 4, 9 in SM1] and 0.425–4.57 GPa [references 3, 4, 9 in SM1] respectively; the average tensile strength and Young's moduli for the aligned PAN nano-fibres produced in the current study were 76.71 ± 3.34 MPa and 4.05 ± 1.17 GPa for the UV-curable adhesive end-tab. (ii) Stretching the aligned mat is seen to increase the tensile properties of the electro-spun nano-fibres. (iii) The tensile properties of the aligned

electro-spun PAN fibres are superior to the randomly oriented mats. (iv) Carbonisation of electro-spun PAN nano-fibres is observed to increase the mechanical properties significantly [references 1 and 2 in SM1].

4. Conclusions

Extensive trials were carried out to establish the optimum way to end-tab the electro-spun aligned PAN nano-fibres. It was demonstrated that the photo-curable UV resin was the ideal end-tab adhesive in the current case because: (i) it was possible to prevent the resin from seeping into the fibres in the gauge length region; (ii) the viscosity of the resin could be controlled by photo-irradiation such that it could be applied precisely over the end-tab region; and (iii) the shrinkage upon UV irradiation to cross-link the resin was minimal. The tensile test results of the test specimens using UV adhesive in the end-tabs showed a relatively consistent behaviour with the highest average UTS (76.7 ± 3.3 MPa) and Young's modulus (4.05 ± 1.17 GPa) and an average failure strain (23.26 ± 1.46 %). The tensile strength and Young's modulus for the super-glue and the double-side adhesive tape were 68.80 ± 4.41 and 67.38 ± 2.21 MPa respectively, and 2.5 ± 0.53 and 1.86 ± 0.53 GPa respectively; the corresponding failure strains were 23.73 ± 2.23 % and 22.46 ± 2.88 % respectively. Since the processing of the nano-fibre arrays was kept as consistent as practically possible, the superior performance of the UV adhesive is attributed to efficient impregnation of the nano-fibres and better control over the impregnated area. The feasibility of using TEM to measure the cross-sectional area of the aligned electro-spun nano-fibre array was demonstrated.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Siheng Shao: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Surya D. Pandita:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Yuting Liu:** Methodology, Investigation. **Boru An:** Methodology, Investigation. **Theresa Morris:** Methodology, Investigation. **Tao Ma:** Methodology, Investigation. **Gerard F. Fernando:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Gerard Fernando & Siheng Shao has patent #2110133.3 & 2019800920669 issued to Gerard Fernando & Siheng Shao. NA If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2024.108645>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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